

A study to assess the effectiveness of video assisted teaching on knowledge regarding prevention, first aid management and treatment of snake bite among farmers in selected areas of punjab

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Abstract:

Snake bites are an important public health issue, primarily in rural regions where agriculturalists, including the farmers, face a high threat. Inability to understand information on prevention, first aid treatment, and cure of snake bites often leads to severe complications resulting in death. This quasi-experimental study attempts to assess the video-assisted teaching (VAT) intervention with regard to farmers' knowledge concerning the prevention, first aid treatment, and the treatment of snake bites in select areas of Punjab.

Data were collected using a structured knowledge questionnaire, which covered various aspects of snake bite prevention, immediate first aid measures, and appropriate treatment protocols. The experimental group was engaged in an interactive session that used a video-assisted teaching module, which was specifically designed in the local language to ensure better understanding and engagement. The control group received no intervention. Pre-test assessment: The baseline knowledge of both groups was low. Most participants were unaware of the critical preventive measures and appropriate first aid management of snake bites.

Video- assisted teaching can be a pragmatic, scalable approach to propagating critical health information for vulnerable populations to proactively manage snake bite incidents. The need for further research and integration of such interventions within established public health frameworks is therefore suggested. The conclusion of this study is that video-assisted teaching significantly improves the knowledge base of farmers with respect to preventing, first-aid management of, and treatments for snake bites.

Keywords:

Snake bites, farmers' knowledge, questionnaire, Video- assisted teaching etc.
